

Synthesis and magnetic properties of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ core/shell nanoparticles

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Abstract : Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles were synthesized by a novel, simple and cost effective co-precipitation method. The products were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra, (high-resolution) transmission electron microscopy (HR) TEM, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and magnetic hysteresis loops. After the annealing process at 350 °C, the Fe_2O_3 coating can protect the Fe core from oxidation effectively. And the formed $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ core/shell structure shows better magnetic behavior, which is promising in targeted drug delivery systems.

Keywords : Nanostructured materials, magnetic measurements, $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ core/shell nanomaterials, iron oxide, magnetite.

Introduction

Transition metal oxides have been of scientific and technological interest for many decades due to their interesting optical, magnetic, electrical and catalytical properties. Among these, magnetite (Fe_3O_4) is a common magnetic iron oxide that has a cubic inverse spinel structure with *fcc* close packed oxygens and Fe cations occupying interstitial tetrahedral and octahedral sites¹. Magnetic unit cell can be represented with the formula $(\text{Fe}_8^{3+})_A[\text{Fe}_{40/3}^{3+} \text{Fe}_{8/3}^{2+}]_B\text{O}_{32}$, where A and B indicates tetrahedral and octahedral positioning, respectively. The electrons can hop between Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions in the octahedral sites at room temperature, rendering magnetite an important class of half-metallic materials^{2,3}. Magnetic nanoparticles, and more particularly magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), have been widely used for biomedical applications such as cell targeting, cell separation, drug delivery, hyperthermia^{4,5}, or in environmental sciences, for metal separation from wastewater⁶.

Due to their magnetic moment, magnetic nanoparticles can be driven by an applied magnetic field into specific regions of the human body for *in vivo* applications. For *in vivo* diagnosis or for metal separation, magnetic separa-

tion and selection can be done. For these applications, magnetic nanoparticles have to become magnetized at low magnetic field. However, in order to avoid any agglomeration phenomenon, the magnetic nanoparticles must not present magnetic remanence, i.e. must have zero magnetization in the absence of an applied magnetic field. This particular behavior is achieved with superparamagnetic nanoparticles. Typically, magnetite nanoparticles become superparamagnetic at sizes below ~ 15 nm.

Chemical synthesis of colloidal magnetite has been known for a long time : aqueous mixture of ferric and ferrous salts is mixed with an alkali in order to induce the precipitation of magnetite particles (maghemite can then be obtained by soft oxidation of magnetite)⁷. The average diameter of particles can be tuned between 5–100 nm by varying experimental conditions (concentration, temperature, nature of alkali, ionic strength, agitation, etc.) but the system is always polydispersed in size^{8,9} due to the Oswald ripening mechanism (the large particles will grow at the cost of small ones)^{10,11}. Organized assemblies or complex structures have been used as nanoreactors (microemulsions, vesicle, polymer matrix media synthesis) in order to obtain nearly monodispersed ultrafine iron oxide nanoparticles.

In practice, even if better control can actually be done over the size and the size distribution of nanoparticles, progress in the use of superparamagnetic nanoparticles depends on the improvement of synthetic methods. In the paper we propose a completely new process based on coprecipitation of magnetite in ethanol media, which yields nanoparticles with a controlled distribution avoiding the use of nanoreactors.

Experimental

Materials :

Analytical $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and NaOH were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich are of analytical grade and used without any further purification.

Preparation of magnetite nanocrystals :

Typically, 0.54 g of $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.26 g of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were dissolved into concentrated 0.05 M hydrochloric acid solution under N_3 flow, 30 min prior to the use, to ensure inert atmosphere. After stirring for about 30 min, 1.5 M NaOH solution was added dropwise into 250 ml three-neck flask under vigorous mechanical stirring at room temperature (30 °C). A black precipitate immediately formed. After stirring for about 30 min, the precipitate was separated by applying an external magnetic field, and the supernatant was removed from the precipitation by decantation. The obtained black precipitation sample 1 (S1) was collected by centrifugation at

5000 rpm after washing several times with ethanol and distilled water, following dried at 100 °C for 1 h in vacuum.

Preparation of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ core/shell nano-materials :

The resultant $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@ \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ core/shell structures were obtained by calcining in air at 350 °C for 2.5 h in H_2 gas atmosphere, with color change from black to red-brown as denoted as sample 2 (S2).

Characterization :

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were measured using a Rigaku D/max 2500 VB/PC diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm). Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were recorded on an American Nicolet FTIR 55XC spectrometer using KBr pellet. The morphologies of the products were characterized by transmission electron microscope (TEM, JEM-2100), high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM, JEOL-2100F) and scanning electron microscope (LEO 1430 VP). The magnetic properties at 300 K were measured using quantum-design physical property measurement system with maximum magnetic field of 9T (PPMS-9T).

XRD analysis :

The phase investigation of the crystallized product was performed by XRD and the pattern is shown in Fig. 1 of the obtained S1. The XRD pattern indicates that the prod-

Fig. 1. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of Sample 1.

uct is iron oxide, Fe₃O₄, and the diffraction peaks are broadened owing to small crystallite size typical for nanomaterials and also for ultra small crystalline materials where diffraction peaks cannot be well resolved. All the diffraction peaks could be well indexed as cubic structures of Fe₃O₄, consistent with the standard value (JCPDS No. 01-1111) indicating a high phase purity of iron oxide. The lattice parameter “*a*” for the synthesized iron oxide nanoparticles was refined using TREOR 90 program¹² and “*a*” was obtained 8.378 ± 0.004 Å. This value is between the lattice parameters of magnetite, Fe₃O₄ (8.393 Å, JCPDS No. 19-629), and maghemite, γ-Fe₂O₃ (8.3515 Å JCPDS No. 39-1346), both of which have spinel structure. Maghemite has basically the same crystal as magnetite, however it can also be considered as an Fe²⁺-deficient magnetite with formula (Fe₈³⁺)_A[Fe_{40/3}³⁺Fe_{8/3}²⁺]_BO₃₂, where Fe_{8/3}²⁺ represents a vacancy, A indicates tetrahedral positioning and B octahedral. The obtained phase has an intermediate lattice parameter which could be defined as non-stoichiometric magnetite, showing that a partial oxidation probably occurs in air. Indeed, Fe²⁺ cations in nanoparticles are not thermodynamically stable in air. Because of the high reactivity of nanoparticles, they are easily oxidized into Fe³⁺ in air. The cell parameter decreases linearly as the deviation, δ, from stoichiometry (in Fe_{3-δ}O₄) increases¹³⁻¹⁶. Calculations of δ purely based on the lattice parameter for our case yielded δ as 0.15 (Fe_{2.85}O₄). Although the crystalline phase has lattice parameter very close to magnetite, this deviation in stoichiometry may be attributed to a surface oxidation of approximately 30% of Fe²⁺ ions. On the basis of the Scherrer equation¹⁷, using the width of most intense diffraction line, the average crystallite size for Fe₃O₄ was found as ~15 nm, however it is found as unreliable at estimating particle size, because the assumption of an underlying crystal structure (translational symmetry) is often invalid¹⁸. Therefore, in order to test the reliability of estimated crystallite size from Scherrer equation, we use the diffraction profile fitting to estimate the size using Wejrzanowski *et al.*⁽¹⁹⁻²³⁾ of the magnetic γ-Fe₂O₃ thin layer on the surface of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles. This idea was proved by S2. From the red-brown body color of S2, we can infer that there exists the phase of γ-Fe₂O₃ on the surface of S2. From TEM images (shown in Fig. 2), we can observe that S2 has a little agglomeration after calcinations, but the average size of the spherical S2 does not increase obviously, which is compared to the S1.

Fig. 2. TEM images : (a) Sample 1 and (b) Sample 2.

The FTIR of S2 further showed that the characteristic absorption bands of α-FeOOH disappeared in S2.

Magnetic properties characterization :

Magnetization measurements of iron oxide nanoparticles were performed using VSM technique and results at 300 K are shown in Fig. 3a and b. The saturation magnetization (*M_s* calculated from a plot of *M* vs 1/*H* (*M* at 1/*H* ≥ 0)) value of the sample is measured as 1.94 emu/cm³ at 300 K. These values are comparatively lower than that of bulk magnetite with an *M_s* of 480–500 emu/cm³²⁴⁻²⁷. The magnetization of Fe₃O₄ and γ-Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles increase with external magnetic field strength however, it did not reach the saturation state yet under a high magnetic field of 5 kOe, as observed in earlier works²⁸⁻³¹. The reduction of the *M_s* in Fe₃O₄ with a particle size of 11 nm can be attributed partly to the presence of non-magnetic (dead) surface layer, perhaps due to compositional variations, superparamagnetic relaxation and spin canting because of antiferromagnetic interactions among the Fe spins in the nanostructured materials^{31,32}. The hysteresis curves of Fe₃O₄ and γ-Fe₂O₃ exhibit a coercivity of 546.5 and 121 Oe at 300 K respectively.

Fig. 3. Magnetization curves : (a) Sample 1 and (b) Sample 2.

The magnetic properties of the two samples were also compared at room temperatures. As shown in Fig. 3, both the samples exhibit a typical superparamagnetic behavior, but S2 has a higher saturation magnetization value than S1. There may be two things to account for this phenomenon. First, at a higher temperature, the crystal may grow perfectly and that can contribute to magnetization values. Further, the presence of γ -Fe₂O₃ instead of α -FeOOH in S2, as α -FeOOH has an antiferromagnetic behavior, if also contributes to the magnetic saturation values.

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